

REMOTE SENSING APPLICATIONS AND INTERACTIVE
ANALYSES IN MARINE FISHERIES RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

The combination of remotely sensed data, in-situ data, and now fairly routine interactive analysis techniques is a powerful way to examine marine phenomena, and to further explore and understand relationships between organisms and their ocean environment. Although such analyses are being performed in special cases on several systems, a system has yet to be developed and fully exploited by marine fisheries researchers.

At the present time, fishery biologists can handle most short term data requirements of fishery managers, at least for those species that are reasonably well understood. Long term predictions are, however, still difficult if not impossible. Research priorities for fishery (and biological oceanographers generally) have changed little in the past fifty years, although great progress has been made in specific disciplines (e.g. taxonomy, ecology, behavior, life history and distribution). The reason for lack of progress in predicting longer term variations in population strength and species composition is simple enough. Such are largely dependent on our ability to predict fluxes and change in the physical environment. (Edwards & Kirkley, 1983).

The progress made in the last fifty years came about largely through effective use of research vessels. Research vessels, however, move relatively slowly and can only easily detect significant larger scale events. Scientists must resort to detailed and involved statistical analyses of their data to derive information concerning the smaller scale phenomena of the ocean and the distribution of its inhabitants. It is now recognized that at least some of the "stochastic" sieves that organisms, particularly the younger stages, must pass through are a function of the varied and ever-present short time and

space scale events that vessel data cannot provide easily.

With the advent of two notable types of sensors on polar orbiting satellites, i.e. the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) and the Coastal Zone Color Scanner (CZCS) daily observations of the distribution of sea surface temperature and of the distribution of plant pigments are possible. The data provided can be used to improve the efficiency of research vessel operations as they are carried out, and to ask many important retrospective questions concerning the effects of the ocean environment, in all its complexity, on its inhabitants (Brown and Cheney, 1983; NAFO Scientific Council Studies, 1981).

The Northeast Fisheries Center (NEFC) has achieved some level of competence and capability in the use of remotely sensed data. The efforts involved and the difficulties dealt with along the way are a story in themselves. There is, however, one general problem that has always existed and with which we continue to deal. The argument usually boils down to one of the need for accuracy in the strictest sense and the often overblown expectation that the instrument itself will somehow directly answer difficult questions. In biological oceanography our first and overwhelming priority is for data on the scale of phenomena, less so for accuracy per se. In this regard satellite data serves our purposes admirably.

At NEFC, the program has a strong biological oceanographic research emphasis. Consistent with the mandate to provide information pertinent to the management of fishery resources, as well as dealing with marine pollution problems, a great deal of monitoring is done. The area of interest extends from Cape Hatteras to Nova Scotia and from the Gulf Stream inshore to the limits of tidal action. From a physical and biological oceanographic point of view, this

area of the ocean is in a constant state of flux.

The following questions are asked of the environment and the biota: what, where, when, how much, how often, and why: remote sensing deals very well with questions like these at least at the surface of the ocean, and not infrequently, if indirectly, right to the bottom. On the continental shelf, as mentioned before, the overwhelming priority for us is that of a better understanding of the scale of phenomena and less so absolute measurements. The instruments are precise enough, if not always as accurate as one might desire. They won't replace vessels in the near future, both because constant ground truth data is still necessary and because sensors do not deal directly with the water column, and certainly not with most of the creatures in it which are also of direct concern to us. Satellite data can, however, greatly modify the manner in which cruises are carried out. Features with which we are concerned show up clearly in satellite images. We would like to follow the progress of some of these on a daily basis, others less frequently. Examples of the features of interest include (see also Table 1):

In the slope water:

The Gulf Stream rings and meanders which perturb and entrain shelf water with the potential consequence of stripping off biota (e.g. fish eggs and larvae) (Armstrong, 1982).

On the Continental Shelf:

In the Hudson Canyon area, warm core rings intersect the bottom and create currents that are strong enough to displace fixed fishing gear like crab and lobster pots (Chamberlin, 1982).

A major feature at the outer edge of the continental shelf, of particular interest to biological oceanographers since it effects distribution of resources, is the shelf-slope front. This front may vary a great deal in its position from time to time. Tracking these shifts in position is only possible using satellite data (Armstrong, 1982).

The front along the northern edge of Georges Bank separates the waters of Georges Bank from the Gulf of Maine and represents surface boundary of one of the richest fishing grounds in the world. Thus, it is of interest to researchers and managers alike. Each of these water masses, those of Georges Bank and the Gulf of Maine, are distinctly visible

because of their differing surface temperatures.

Along the coast:

The upwelling and mixing areas of Nan-tucket Shoals and Georges Bank are reasonably constant phenomena though they vary somewhat through time.

Coastal upwelling is less consistent. It is usually the result of strong winds from a particular direction. An example—the practical significance of such upwelling is seen on the coast of Maine. Dr. Clarice Yentsch (Hurst and Yentsch, 1981) and colleagues have suggested that the upwelling controlled by northeasterly winds here may trigger the onset of paralytic shellfish poisoning.

Along the coast of New Jersey, particularly the northern part, coastal upwelling is of significant interest because of the possibility of bringing inshore materials disposed of further offshore.

The timing and volume of estuarine and riverine outflow is of particular concern to those dealing with ocean productivity and pollution because of materials that are carried onto the continental shelf from the estuaries where they may impact resources. In this connection NEFC has carried out, jointly with NASA/Langley and several institutions in the Chesapeake Bay region, a study of a wide array of sensors having potential for monitoring estuarine and riverine plumes and their contents. The work was reported in a volume entitled Chesapeake Bay Plume Study-Superflux 1980, NASA Conference Publication 2188.

As mentioned above, much of our work is concerned with monitoring physical conditions and the biota throughout our region. Depending upon the nature of the study, it takes from one to two months to cover the entire region by vessel. In most cases the cruises are designed to carry out a stratified random survey pattern of sampling. Over an area as large as this, one does get useful general estimates in macroscale of all those things in which we are interested and the data bases become more valuable with the passage of years. Such cruises, however, cannot cope with the dynamics of water movement and seasonal change since much of what happens occurs over a relatively short period of time and is significant both in meso- and micro-scale. For all practical purposes, we poke holes in the ocean at discrete points in time and space. These data may be analyzed in various ways but they are traditionally presented in the form of a hand-contoured

plot. When the cruises take one month to complete, the final data set is hardly synoptic. Needless to say, any estimates, as for example an estimate of the total chlorophyll in the water column, are biased as a consequence. Generally, data matches well for the time when the vessel samples and the satellite data coincide and less well with each day of difference in timing.

There are many challenges and difficulties, however, when using satellite data. The first of these, of course, is simply that of cloud cover. We would like to follow some aspects of ocean flux on a daily basis. That, however, is clearly impossible. To give you some idea of the seasonal changes of cloud cover, in our search through archives we have found that one can expect to see any particular area, on the average, every second or third day during the warmer months of the year (March through September). During the colder months, October through February, once a week is about all you can expect, and many areas not even once a month. It should be noted that at any season, it is also possible to have data for any particular part of the region for many days in a row.

Atmospheric conditions other than clouds vary daily. Recently, volcanic ash affected the signal received by satellite sensors. At the time the full effect that it had on the signal was not known. This simply underscores the need for maintaining a continuous body of ground truth data.

The third is that of dealing with the complexity associated with the depth to which sensors penetrate. Pigment algorithms are improving and provide more than general estimates in answer to the "how much" question. In the meantime, however, sensors are providing vital information on the scales and timing of primary production as well as temperature. Once again, ground truth is critically important. (Platt and Herman, 1983).

A fourth is dissolved organic material (DOM) or gelbstuff. It does tend to confuse, and often obfuscate the estimation of pigment, especially near-shore and in areas where there is significant river runoff. (Austin, 1979; Hojerslev, 1981).

After several years of using retrospective imagery, Dr. J.L. Chamberlin, (Chamberlin, 1982) then at the National Marine Fisheries Service, has accumulated

a great deal of knowledge concerning the formation, movement and ultimate dissolution of warm core rings. To deal with the realtime need for warm core ring information to be used in conjunction with the National Science Foundation funded program, NEFC established a cooperative venture with NASA/Goddard, Direct Read-out Project, to get, in real-time (+ 30 minutes) high resolution, appropriately enhanced, sectorized and gridded AVHRR thermal data. The imagery was transmitted over a telephone line to the Atlantic Environmental Group at the Narragansett Lab of the Northeast Fisheries Center, where it was put into chart form and then transmitted via satellite (ATS) to the vessels at sea. In turn, the vessels used the information to guide their sampling. The images received from NASA/Goddard were of significant operational assistance in carrying out the warm core ring project.

It is clear that there is a need to improve accessibility to satellite data to deal with near-real-time needs. To this end, there are several regional efforts underway to deal with such issues in the broadest sense. One of these is the Northeast Area Remote Sensing System (NEARSS) Association. Another is EPRSS, the Eastern Pacific Remote Sensing System, now developing in the Northwest, following in the footsteps of NEARSS.

For many years now, meteorologists have used remotely sensed data both to improve their short range predictions and to further develop their ability to make longer term predictions of climatic trends. Recently the PROFS system for the interactive analysis of various meteorological data bases was developed for this purpose. PROFS will be discussed later in this session by Dr. Peter Mandics. Also later in the session, Roland Nagle will discuss a similar system developed for the Navy. The ability of marine biologists to provide longer term predictions depends, in good part, on the progress made by those interested in weather and climate. Both groups need satellite data. And, in a great many respects, the problems (in the conceptual sense at least) that each group is dealing with are the same.

The same equipment and same techniques that were developed for the analyses of satellite data may also be used for the analysis of data from research vessels. And, with the incorporation of additional methods used specifically for the manipulations of biological data, it is possible to develop a very powerful tool for interactive analyses of satellite data with physical and/or biological

research vessel data. To some extent, we've explored various interactive procedures, (some of which Andrew Tvirbutas will present later in this session), and concluded that the potential is enormous but the surface has barely been scratched.

In performing interactive analyses an investigator gets a new perspective on the information at hand, new ideas, new leads to solutions, more thorough understanding of relationships between parameters used and thus a better handle on the affect of variables in processes which in turn affect the condition (or abundance) of stocks of marine animals.

Software developed for remote sensing data processing can be applied to biological, and physical oceanographic data. Distributional data, obtained

through groundfish surveys and commercial landings, with appropriate adjustments, may be interacted with physical oceanographic data. The results help to demonstrate the preference of species to a particular parameter.

Interactive analyses and visual displays of a variety of data from various sources will allow marine scientists, for example, to get further insight into the factors influencing primary production and to look into the relationships of fish concentrations observed by hydro-acoustic methods with fronts that may be seen in satellite imagery as well as other interesting, and to this point, unsolved problems of concern to the fisheries scientist.

TABLE 1

*Phenomena	**Relative Sensor Usefulness			Why	Frequency of Coverage Desired
	AVHRR	GOES	CZCS		
Cloud cover, - type & amount - short term changes	1	2	1	Affects biological processes and temperature change	continuous
Gulf Stream meanders	1	2	3	Creates major frontal systems in slope water to which high seas pelagics respond, e. g. swordfish, tuna	every 3 days in region
Warm core rings (and other major frontal systems in slope water)	1	2	3	a. Entrain shelf water b. Create strong bottom currents along continental shelf edge, disturbing lobster traps	every 3 days
Shelf slope front	1	2		Affects the distribution patterns and migration of shelf biota	every week
Persistent frontal systems on the shelf:					
a. delineate water masses, e. g. Georges Bank	1		2	a. Relative openness of gyre determines strength of year class	every 3 days
b. delineate local upwelling, e. g. Nantucket Shoals and Georges Bank	1		2	b. Degree (amount & timing) of upwelling determines input of nutrients	
Significant transient phenomena					
a. Estuarine outflow	1		2	a. Deposition of pollutants onto the continental shelf	every 3-7 days
b. Fresh water runoff	2		1	b. Deposition of solids, input of nutrients	every 3-7 days
c. Wind generated coastal upwelling	1			c. Prediction of potential PSP outbreak	every 48 hours
Timing & distribution of primary production			1	Base of food chain	depending upon season & area, daily to weekly
Surface Temperature	1	2		Timing of migratory movements	once every 3 days
Operational guidance of research vessel operations	1	3	2	Improves vessel efficiency	as often as cloud-free coverage is available (real-time)

*Phenomena of interest to NEFC scientists.

**Relative usefulness of sensor is indicated by number with 1 most useful, 2 less so, etc.

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